

Epistemic Twins: Enabling a Symbolic Science of Language Model Knowledge

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Abstract

Large Language Models (LLMs) are impactful yet opaque artifacts. At their core, they are subsymbolic constructs defined by billions of numeric weights that interact in a largely inscrutable manner. Current analysis paradigms are either black-box benchmarks that test model performance on pre-defined tasks, or mechanistic interpretability approaches that trace back outputs to specific weights. Both analysis methods are limited by the experimenter’s hypothesis space - one must know what to look for to find it. In this perspective, we argue for a third, radically different analysis paradigm: **Epistemic Twins**. We propose constructing large-scale symbolic approximations of LLMs in human-readable formats. This enables the comprehensive materialization of factual knowledge (or beliefs) inherent in the model without predefining hypotheses, facilitating large-scale analysis and auditing towards better understanding and explainability.

1 Introduction

LLMs have transformed machine intelligence, and serve as the cornerstone of the current wave of artificial intelligence. Despite their impact, our understanding of their functioning and capabilities remains vague. The public discourse is often driven by hyped marketing language, with only a weak grounding in rigorous statistical or theoretical analyses of LLM knowledge and functioning. Consequently, there is a significant barrier to LLM deployment in safety-critical applications.

Currently, two paradigms dominate the analysis of LLMs (see Fig. 1):

1. *Black-box benchmarks*: This approach ignores the internal functioning of LLMs and focuses on its input-output-behavior in test cases, often prompting it with thousands of them to assess specific capabilities (Ribeiro et al., 2020; Chang et al., 2024). While most

Figure 1: Three paradigms for analyzing LLMs. Benchmarks operate at reasonable scale, but do not enable factual tracing nor are hypothesis-free. Circuit tracing enables tracing, but is hard to scale, and requires narrow hypotheses. We propose Epistemic Twins as novel analysis paradigm.

common, this paradigm is inherently limited by the coverage of the benchmarks (“availability bias” (Tversky and Kahneman, 1973)); it cannot reveal behaviors or knowledge not anticipated by the benchmark designers (Raji et al., 2021; Bean and others, 2025).

2. *Circuit tracing (mechanistic interpretability)*: This approach attempts to open the black box, tracing responses back to individual circuits and neurons to establish causal links (Rai et al., 2024). While this enables real explainability, it is computationally expensive and fragile to distribution shifts, with possibly parallel explanations for a single task, and offers little insight into the global knowledge state of the model (Méloux et al., 2025; Sharkey

et al., 2025; Somvanshi et al., 2026).

In light of these limitations, we advocate for a third, complementary and novel paradigm: **Epistemic Twins**. An epistemic twin is a symbolic, comprehensive and comprehensible model of the factual knowledge stored within an LLM, stored in a classical relational or RDF database/knowledge base.

If this epistemic twin is sufficiently faithful to its parametric LLM, i.e., approximates its knowledge well, then LLM providers and users can then answer questions about the epistemic state of the LLM by established database technology over the epistemic twin.

Epistemic twins offer four opportunities:

1. **Scaling:** They can offer insights about a sample of unprecedented size, or even the entirety of an LLM’s knowledge, containing millions of entities and hundreds of million of assertions, where even large benchmarks only operate at the scale of a few tens of thousands of instances.
2. **Factual tracing:** They enable to trace LLM responses to factual prompts to specific statements within (or not represented in) the epistemic twin. This way, LLM behavior can be explained by its knowledge state.
3. **No weight access needed:** Unlike mechanistic interpretability, which requires access to an LLM’s weights, epistemic twins can be constructed even for API-only models (see Sec. 3).
4. **Hypothesis-free:** They are hypothesis-free human-readable representations of the LLMs knowledge, i.e., they do not underlie the cognitive availability bias (Tversky and Kahneman, 1973) that benchmarks and circuit tracing face, where the experiment designers predisposition crucially limits the possible experiment results.¹

In this perspective, we present both the idea of epistemic twins, as well as a call to action. We argue that for auditability, it should become a standard that akin to other documentation in model cards (Mitchell et al., 2019), model providers release epistemic twins along with newly released LLMs. We

¹Of course, any individual analysis conducted on top of an epistemic twin still require a hypothesis, therefore, we used the symbol (✓) in Fig. 1.

proceed by introducing the concept of epistemic twins (Section 2), their construction (Section 3), formal approaches to estimate approximation quality (Section 4), and exemplar analyses enabled by symbolic twins (Section 5). We conclude with a perspective on cost and a call for action (Section 6).

2 What is an Epistemic Twin?

The central premise of our case relies on two observations.

1. **Translating subsymbolic knowledge into symbolic form:** LLM knowledge is by default subsymbolic and numeric: When one downloads a model, all one gets are billions of real-valued weights, with no apparent meaning or interpretation. To be truly auditable, this subsymbolic form must be translated into a human-readable, symbolic form.
2. **Comprehensive knowledge mapping:** Current assessment by benchmarks is sample-based, and hence strongly subject to experimenter bias. An epistemic twin aims to extract the *entirety* of the LLM’s factual knowledge, thereby enabling serendipitous discoveries and statistical analyses over the whole underlying knowledge base.

An epistemic twin manifests as a database or knowledge base (KB) (Weikum et al., 2021), which provides both a human-readable data format, and a format readily accessible to statistical analysis via SQL or SPARQL queries.

The reader may question how epistemic twins differs from simply releasing an LLM’s training corpus, as available, e.g., for the OLMo series (Dirk Groeneveld and others, 2024; Olmo Team, 2025). We emphasize that training corpora serve the purpose of pipeline reproducibility, not explainability. Knowing that a fact existed in the training data does not guarantee the LLM learned it (Kandpal et al., 2023), nor does it reveal the hallucinations, false inferences, or conflation the model generated during training. An epistemic twin represents the post-training *learned state*, not the pre-training input.

3 How to Construct Epistemic Twins

Locating and isolating knowledge in LLMs from other capabilities has been advocated by various works (Geva et al., 2021; Meng et al., 2022;

Mahowald et al., 2024). Large-scale extraction and transformation of LLM knowledge into symbolic form is an emerging field, yet promising approaches already exist. Cohen et al. (2023) introduced LMCrawl, a recursive prompt pipeline for extracting the internalized knowledge graph by a breadth-first search (BFS). This method was scaled by Hu et al. (2025) as the GPTKB methodology, to enable the concurrent extraction of millions of entities and statements. The process can be formalized as a graph traversal algorithm over the latent knowledge graph inside the LLM:

1. **Seed Initialization:** The process begins with a set of seed entities (e.g., a list of popular head entities).
2. **Recursive Expansion:** The system prompts the LLM to generate relational triples (Subject, Predicate, Object) associated with the current entities.
3. **Traversal:** The objects of the generated triples become new subject nodes for the next iteration.
4. **Termination:** The recursion continues until a stopping criterion is met, such as graph depth, a compute budget, or a confidence threshold (e.g., when the average confidence of newly discovered facts drops below 90%).

Epistemic twins can be constructed open-domain, or restricted to a specific topic. In the open-domain, Hu et al. (2025) constructed *GPTKB v1* (Hu et al., 2025) and *GPTKB v1.5* (Hu et al., 2026), recursive extractions from GPT-4o-mini and GPT-4.1, respectively, covering 3-6M entities and 100M statements each. For topic-specific extractions, Giordano and Razniewski (2026) showed how the GPTKB methodology can be restricted in scope, and constructed *babylonGPTKB*, *tBBTGPTKB* and *dax40GPTKB*, comprising 13k, 1k and 2k statements, respectively, extracted from GPT-4.1-mini.

Further methodologies exist, for instance, non-recursive list-based extraction schemes (Hao et al., 2023; Parović et al., 2025), taxonomic knowledge (Funk et al., 2023; Zeng et al., 2024), or a text-oriented adaptation that has already extracted 1M Wikipedia-style articles (Saeed and Razniewski, 2026). The underlying codes are publicly released and easily deployed against public as well as private LLM endpoints, hence, we expect a prolifer-

ation of similar knowledge extractions in the near future.

4 How Can we Guarantee Twinning Fidelity?

For epistemic twins to be useful, one must be able to assess their *twinning fidelity*, i.e., the degree to which they truly reflect the parametric knowledge inside the modeled LLM. We propose three key dimensions of twinning fidelity:

1. **Twinning accuracy (precision):** The fraction of assertions in the epistemic twin that are actually beliefs held by the twinned LLM.²
2. **Twinning coverage (recall):** The fraction of (factual) beliefs of the LLM that are contained in the epistemic twin.
3. **Twin determinism (reproducibility):** The degree to which twin construction is a reproducible process.

The perfect twin would be 100% accurate, cover all of the twinned LLM’s knowledge, and be unique. However, as LLMs are probabilistic constructs, perfect twinning is not possible. We propose the following approaches to measure twinning fidelity:

1. For twinning accuracy, for a given *s-p-o* triple in the twin, one can simply prompt the LLM with *s* and *p* (and some paraphrases), and observe whether *o* is indeed returned by the LLM. For example, for GPTKB v1.5, this way, we observe a twinning accuracy of 74%.
2. For twinning coverage, one can use abundance estimators from ecology on random walks over the model’s knowledge graph (Luggen et al., 2019), or BFS property extrapolation (Kurant et al., 2011), to predict the fraction of all factual knowledge covered within the epistemic twin. For example, for GPTKB v1.5, by BFS run extrapolation, we estimate a coverage of 42% of all named entities within GPT-4.1.
3. For twin determinism, one can use repeated runs of the twin construction process with

²Note that *Twinning accuracy* should not be mixed up with the Twin’s *factual accuracy*. For example, GPTKB v1.0 is reported to have a factual accuracy of 31%, i.e., 31% of its statements are true w.r.t. the real-world, but its twinning accuracy relative to GPT-4o-mini is far higher, at around 60%. The converse, i.e., a high factual accuracy, but low Twinning accuracy, is also possible.

Analysis	Method	Example from GPT-4.1 twin (GPTKB v1.5)
Topical coverage	Count relevant entities	GPT-4.1 knows more than 1M persons and more than 100k companies .
Gender bias	Count gender identity facts	GPT-4.1 has a positive bias towards females (1.16:1); however, this strongly flips outside English-language nationalities.
Sensitive content	Search for sensitive attributes	GPT-4.1 stores virtually no private phone numbers and addresses, but thousands of statements about ethnic, religious, and sexual identities.
Logical consistency	Check satisfaction of logical rules	GPT-4.1’s knowledge is highly inconsistent: only 15% of border-relation facts are present in both directions.
Knowledge cutoff	Observe latest dates	GPT-4.1’s knowledge cutoff is mid-2024 .

Table 1: Examples of analyses enabled by epistemic twins. Taken from (Ghosh et al., 2025).

different seed nodes or random seeds, and observe the overlap in the resulting twins. For example, based on repeated runs of the construction process for babylonGPTKB, it was observed that repeated runs overlap in roughly two thirds of their named entities, even from different starting entities (Giordano and Razniewski, 2026). This indicates that despite some variability, “belief structure” remains largely consistent across extraction runs.

Of course, the fidelity dimensions and metrics proposed above are only a start. Future research will extend and refine the methods for defining and measuring twinning fidelity.

5 What Analyses Are Enabled by Epistemic Twins?

The existence of an epistemic twin can transform LLM research and certification. It enables:

- Quantification of Knowledge:** We can complement estimates via parameter counts (Allen-Zhu and Li, 2024) with estimates based on counting actual “knowledge units” (facts). This allows us to compare models based on information density. For example, based on BFS extrapolation, the GPT-4.1 epistemic twin GPTKB v1.5 can be used to predict that GPT-4.1 knows a total of around 15 M named entities.
- Global Accuracy Estimation:** By evaluating the epistemic twin against reference sources, we can calculate global accuracy scores that are not overfitted to specific benchmark test sets. For example, (Hu et al., 2026) observe a global accuracy of 76% of the GPT-4.1 twin

GPTKB v1.5, well below the numbers reported in typical factuality benchmarks.³

- Bias and Topic Auditing:** An epistemic twin allows for topic modeling over the model’s beliefs. We can visualize the distribution of knowledge (e.g., Western vs. Non-Western history) and detect systemic biases (e.g., gender associations in professional roles) by querying the database rather than probing the model stochastically. More specific examples are given in Table 1.

Such analyses can benefit three types of stakeholders. For **users**, this aids in model selection. For **providers**, it offers a transparency mechanism for accountability. For **regulators**, it provides a tangible artifact to evaluate compliance without needing access to weights or training data.

6 Cost and Call for Action

The construction of epistemic twins is resource-intensive. For example, the GPT-4.1 twin GPTKB v1.5 cost 14,000 \$ in API calls, and accuracy as well as coverage still leave room for improvement.

It is therefore conceivable that high-fidelity epistemic twins may cost hundred thousand dollar, or more. While not insignificant, this still pales in comparison to current LLM training costs, e.g., estimated at \$78M for GPT-4 and \$191M for Gemini Ultra (AI Index Steering Committee, 2024). Given that a twin offers a completely new perspective towards rendering the model interpretable, safe, and auditable, we argue this 0.1% additional investment

³It is important to note that also epistemic twins operate in a precision-recall tradeoff, as LLM knowledge is inherently probabilistic. It is possible to construct different symbolic twins from the same LLM, at a different point of the tradeoff. Alternatively, one could also represent the epistemic twin in a probabilistic database.

is not only justified, but essential for responsible AI development (Mitchell et al., 2019).

Moreover, by appropriately scoping the extraction process, it is also possible to construct epistemic twins only for selected topics (Giordano and Razniewski, 2026). While this severely limits coverage, such focused twinning enables cost-efficient, focused analysis even without significant investments.

We conclude with a call to action. Benchmarks are important to assess capabilities, as is mechanistic interpretability to understand computations. However, to understand model knowledge at scale, and without experimenter bias, a new research investment into epistemic twins is necessary, and timely.

Limitations

Factual knowledge focus Our concept of epistemic twins currently focuses strictly on declarative, factual knowledge. LLMs also possess other knowledge, e.g., procedural knowledge on how to code or multiply, or linguistic knowledge on how to rhyme or argue. These non-factual capabilities are not currently captured by the fact-oriented knowledge graph structure proposed here.

Probabilistic-to-boolean LLMs are inherently probabilistic, while knowledge bases by default represent knowledge in Boolean form (true/false), and the epistemic twins constructed so far follow this representation. A translation from probabilities to a Boolean format necessarily leads to some information loss. It is in principle possible to expand representation to a probabilistic format, though probabilistic databases are much less established, and the translation of LLM-internal token likelihoods into truth probabilities is a nontrivial task as well (Jiang et al., 2020).

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